

Leveraging Nature-based Solutions for Efficient, Resilient, and Sustainable Food Systems in Sub-Saharan Africa

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Sub-Saharan Africa's (SSA) food systems face exclusive, complex, and compounding challenges ranging from climate change susceptibility, water scarcity, land degradation, hyperinflation, poverty, and rapid population growth. Key areas of urgent intervention include ensuring food security, reducing food waste, and promoting sustainable agricultural practices. Policy and practical intervention debates are ongoing. This article contributes to the debate by highlighting the potential of nature-based solutions in transforming SSA's food systems. The article first identifies the challenges of SSA's food systems and then explores how nature-based solutions can contribute to the realisation of efficient, resilient, and sustainable food systems in SSA. Underpinned by a review of primary and secondary sources, the article flags how nature-based solutions can generate climate change resilience, protect biodiversity, empower smallholder farmers, address land degradation, and generate cost-effective food system activities. The article argues, therefore, that leveraging nature-based solutions in SSA's food systems offers a powerful and localised strategy to build efficient, resilient, and sustainable food systems. These solutions not only address environmental concerns but also deliver vital co-benefits for human well-being and economic development.

Keywords: Food systems, nature-based solutions, resilience, sustainability, Sub-Saharan Africa

Sub-Saharan Africa's (SSA) food systems are at a crisis point. They are facing unique and compounding challenges, including climate change vulnerability, land degradation, water scarcity, poverty, and rapid population growth (Abdullahi, Kalengyo, & Warsame, 2024; Bedasa & Deksisa, 2024; Ndhlovu, 2025a). These challenges affect the entire food chain, from production to consumption. Today, the region is among the most food-insecure, with over 20% of the regional population recorded as undernourished in 2023 (FAO et al., 2023). It is projected that by 2030, over 600 million people will be food insecure (World Bank (WB), 2025). Several factors, including environmental and land degradation caused by both natural factors and human activities, are responsible for this crisis. Natural hazards such as droughts, storms, floods, and wildfires emanating from climate change have a significant impact on food production and distribution through direct damage to crops and infrastructure, disrupting supply chains, and generating price increases and food shortages (Farah, Mohamed, & Musse, 2025; Kumari, Dash, Jagadesh, & Singh, 2025; Ndhlovu & Dube, 2024). These impacts excessively affect vulnerable populations, particularly people in rural areas, and can exacerbate existing inequalities. On the other hand, human activities cause deforestation and habitat loss. Industrial and agricultural growth results in the clearing of more forests and other natural ecosystems, impacting biodiversity and contributing to climate change (Zhao, Werku, & Bulto, 2025). Human activities can also lead to soil degradation. For instance,

intensive agricultural practices can exhaust soil fertility, intensify erosion, and reduce long-term agricultural productivity (Saleem, Anwar, & Nawaz, 2024). In addition, agricultural runoff, containing fertilisers, pesticides, and animal waste, can pollute water sources, impacting aquatic life and human health (Farah et al., 2025). Furthermore, human activities, including industrial activities as well as agricultural activities, including livestock production and fertiliser use, contribute to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and worsening climate change (Kumari et al., 2025).

Policymakers, researchers, and activists have recommended several strategies to deal with SSA's food system challenges. These strategies range from contract farming to joint ventures and rapid technological integration (Creppy, Bicknell, & Renwick, 2024; FAO, 2016; Liang, Zhang, Bi, Qi, & Xie, 2025). While these interventions have produced significant positive results, they are implicated in worsening environmental and land degradation. Thus, this article highlights the potential of leveraging nature-based solutions (NbS) to deal with food system challenges, particularly at the production stage.

NbS are defined as actions that utilise, protect, restore, or manage natural or adapted ecosystems to address societal challenges, concurrently providing human well-being, ecosystem services, and biodiversity benefits (Mirsafa, Castaldo, & Lemes de Oliveira, 2025). These solutions are gaining both policy and academic attention as a way to deal with issues such as climate change, food security, water management, and disaster risk reduction by working with rather than against nature (Corgo, Cruz, & Conceição, 2024; Gweshengwe, 2025; Mirsafa et al., 2025). NbS originated in the concept of ecological engineering and is a growing acknowledgment of the potential of ecosystems for addressing environmental and societal challenges. Although the term itself is relatively recent, emerging in the 2000s, the underlying ideas have been developing for decades.

This article (i) identifies the challenges of SSA's food systems

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I have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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and (ii) explores how nature-based solutions can contribute to the realisation of efficient, resilient, and sustainable food systems in SSA. This is part of the continued and committed efforts to find collective solutions to SSA's food system challenges. In addition to existing interventions, the article argues that the NbS approach offers a powerful and localised strategy for building efficient, resilient, and sustainable food systems across the region. NbS addresses environmental concerns and delivers critical co-benefits for human well-being and economic development. This article can benefit many stakeholders, ranging from producers (farmers), policymakers, and researchers to the wider community. Producers can gain an understanding of more sustainable and productive farming practices, while policymakers can be guided to develop more effective and targeted agricultural policies. In addition, the article can help researchers expand their knowledge and contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting NbS. Furthermore, for the community, NbS understanding can help improve food security, environmental resilience, and overall well-being.

The article proceeds as follows: The following two sections review the literature on the nature and condition of SSA's food systems and NbS as a theoretical framework, respectively. An outline of the research methodology follows this. Thereafter, the findings are presented and discussed concurrently. Lastly, conclusions are drawn from the findings and the discussion.

Literature Review: State of Food Systems in Sub-Saharan Africa

SSA's food systems are undergoing a transformation, driven by rapid urbanisation, climate change, food inflation, and shifting dietary patterns (African Union (AU), 2022; Ndhlovu, 2025b). However, reviewed literature shows that regional food systems face substantial challenges that hamper them from adequately meeting the food needs of the continent's growing population and ensuring food security for all (AU, 2024; Chihwai, 2024; Mhlanga & Ndhlovu, 2023; Nyoni, Bruelle, Chikowo, & Andrieu, 2024).

SSA's food systems are unable to serve the regional population. Food insecurity and malnutrition characterise the region (FAO et al., 2023). The region now bears the heaviest load of malnutrition globally, with over 20% of its population undernourished (WB, 2025). Many of the countries in the region are not on track to meet hunger eradication goals (Creppy et al., 2024; Ndhlovu, 2025b). In 2022, about 868 million people were moderately food-insecure, with 342 million being severely food-insecure (FAO et al., 2023). Galani et al. (2023) also found that millions of people in the region suffer from prevalent micronutrient deficiencies. Ndhlovu (2025c) observed that overweight and obesity were already significant public health concerns across the region. The region has already failed to meet the Malabo Declaration targets of ending hunger and all forms of malnutrition by 2025 and Sustainable Development Goal 2 of Zero Hunger by 2030 (Ndhlovu, 2025c).

In East and Southern Africa, the food and nutrition security situation is reported as dire and disarrayed (Creppy et al., 2024; FAO et al., 2023; Nyoni et al., 2024). In January 2025, approximately 61.6 million people were reported as food insecure in East Africa (WB, 2025). Estimates also show that over 11 million children below the age of five and about 4 million pregnant and breastfeeding women and girls are acutely malnourished across SSA, with Ethiopia, Somalia, South Sudan, and Sudan recording the highest levels of malnutrition (FAO, AUC, ECA, & WFP, 2023). In the Democratic

Republic of Congo, conflicts remain volatile, worsening food security and humanitarian needs (ReliefWeb, 2025). In Sudan, Rahamtalla, Medani, Salih, et al. (2025) report that the ongoing conflict is exacerbating the food and nutrition crisis, driven by mass displacement, economic collapse, breakdown of essential services, and restricted humanitarian access. This view is supported by the World Bank (2025) which reported that between December 2024 and May 2025, about 24.6 million people experienced high levels of acute food insecurity in Sudan. About 40% of children in refugee camps and local communities were also reported as chronically malnourished (World Health Organisation (WHO), 2025).

In South Sudan, a confluence of challenges, ranging from flooding, dry spells, lack of resources, and dependence on traditional farming methods, has significantly affected agricultural production (Hassan et al., 2024). The World Bank (2025) also revealed that between December 2024 and March 2025, about 6.1 million people in South Sudan faced high levels of food insecurity. In Ethiopia, Degfachew, Dilnesaw, and Massa (2025) found that food insecurity would persist in 2025 due to conflict, food inflation, and slow livelihood recovery from past crises.

In West and Central Africa, high food prices, worsened by extreme weather events and conflict, have increased food insecurity in many countries (Szöke & Ködmön, 2025). About 50 million people in the two sub-regions faced severe food insecurity since June 2025 (WB, 2025). In Mali, sorghum prices were 10 to 25% higher than in previous years, while millet prices were 15% to 45% higher (WB, 2025). This mainly reflected high transport costs, conflict-related market disruptions, and production deficits in the 2024 cereal harvest in several areas (Leip, Rovenskaya, & Wildemeersch, 2024; Ndhlovu, 2025b; Onyeaka, Siyanbola, Akinsemolu, et al., 2024).

In Burkina Faso, the WB (2025) reports that sorghum and millet prices were up to 55% higher every year in most monitored markets. Localised production deficits because of flooding, strong local demand, and conflict-related market disruptions contributed to higher sorghum prices (Alam, Liu, & Pörtner, 2024). In Niger, millet and sorghum prices were stable in 2025 due to an adequate domestic supply, driven by above-average cereal output in 2024 (WB, 2025). In Nigeria, the average prices of locally produced rice and wheat flour were about double their year-earlier levels (Akpogheli, Chiadika, Edo, et al., 2024). High cereal prices were associated with a confluence of factors, including weak national currency, high transport costs, cereal production shortfalls, and conflict-related market disruptions in several areas (Szöke & Ködmön, 2025). In the reviewed literature, climate change-related natural hazards are the major threat to SSA's food systems.

Climate change impacts disrupt food chains, from production to consumption, by destroying crops and livestock, as well as infrastructure such as communication and road networks (de Jong, Selten, Gitata-Kiriga, et al., 2024; Ndhlovu, 2025a). It also disrupts agricultural calendars, making farming unpredictable and unprofitable (Maphosa & Moyo, 2024). It also leads to desertification and land degradation, reducing the amount of productive farmland (Ndhlovu & Dube, 2024; Onyeaka et al., 2024). Land degradation, which involves desertification, soil erosion, and biodiversity loss, reduces agricultural productivity, increases food costs, and threatens food security (African Development Bank (AfDB), 2024; Bedasa & Deksis, 2024). The exhaustion of soil quality results in lower crop yields, poor pastures, decreased income for farmers, and eventually reduced food availability and quality

(Nébié, Ba, & Giannini, 2021; Onyeaka et al., 2024). Once production is affected, all the other components are unable to function properly. African agriculture is dominated by smallholder farmers who rely on rain-fed farming. This makes SSA farming highly vulnerable to climate variability (Abdullahi et al., 2024). Investment in irrigation infrastructure is vital but often lacking, and yet about 80% of the food consumed on the continent is also produced by smallholder farmers (Ndhlovu & Majova, 2023).

Climate change can also result in the spread of new pests and diseases that affect crops and livestock, further impacting food production and availability. In south-eastern Zimbabwe, Ndhlovu and Dube (2024) found that increasing temperature and declining rainfall amounts had led to the emergence of new types of pests for various food crops. Mafongoya, Gubba, Moodley, Chapoto, Kisten, and Phophi (2019) also reported crop and livestock pests and diseases due to climate change in several countries, including South Africa, Mozambique, Malawi, and Zimbabwe.

In addition, the legacy of colonialism in some SSA countries has created uneven agrarian structures, fragmented institutional landscapes, and hybrid governance structures that still impact contemporary food systems (Hassan, Daoud, & Ibrahim, 2024; Ndhlovu, 2025a). The result has been fragile food value chains. African food value chains are characteristically shorter, less integrated, and less regulated. They rely profoundly on smallholders, open-air markets, and informal retailers (Creppy et al., 2024). There is also limited product processing and fewer intermediaries, meaning producers often capture a minimal share of the value (Marson, 2025).

Low productivity and under-mechanisation are other setbacks to SSA's food systems. Due to adequate mechanisation, SSA agriculture relies heavily on imported inputs and equipment (AfDB, 2024). Low yields, poor farm management practices, and limited access to modern technologies are common features in SSA's food systems (Maphosa & Moyo, 2024; Ndhlovu, 2025b). These challenges are attributed to the poor economies that characterise African countries (Chipfupa & Tagwi, 2021; Ndhlovu, 2020). SSA's food systems are dominated by smallholder farmers who often struggle to enter agricultural value chains due to a lack of resources and appropriate technologies (Ndhlovu, 2025b).

Soil degradation and water scarcity are huge challenges across SSA countries. Soil degradation in SSA is primarily caused by unsustainable agricultural practices, deforestation, overgrazing, limited adoption and integration of replenishment strategies, expansion into marginal areas, unsustainable land use practices, and climate change (Nandi et al., 2025; Salhi et al., 2023). These factors lead to challenges such as soil erosion, nutrient depletion, and reduced soil fertility, impacting food security and livelihood (Nandi et al., 2025).

Water availability is also a growing concern. Water scarcity is now a severe and widespread problem in many SSA countries, with roughly two-thirds of the continent branded as arid or semi-arid (Akpensuen & Rivero, 2025). This is despite SSA possessing a significant portion of the world's freshwater resources (Matimolane & Mathivha, 2025). A blend of factors, such as climate change, rapid population growth, and unequal resource distribution, contributes to the crisis (Ndhlovu, 2025a), hindering regional food system development.

Reviewed literature also posits that there are policy and governance gaps that hinder sustainable food system transformation

in SSA (Creppy et al., 2024; Ndhlovu, 2020; Nyoni et al., 2024). Disjointed policies, inadequate research, and a lack of reliable data hamper evidence-based understanding and effective transformation of food systems (Ndhlovu, 2025c).

In essence, the reviewed literature shows that SSA's food systems are at a critical juncture. They face immense pressures, particularly from climate change and existing fragilities, a rapidly growing population, environmental and land degradation, resource constraints, and policy and governance gaps. Several interventions are also proposed in the literature, ranging from the need for strategic investments, policy reforms, technological adoption, and collaborative efforts. To this growing list of interventions, this article adds NbS.

Theoretical Framework: Nature-Based Solutions

The reviewed literature shows that NbS offer a holistic approach and aim to attain manifold benefits (co-benefits) across environmental, social, and economic spheres (Corgo et al., 2024). For instance, restoring a forest sequesters carbon and improves air quality, conserves biodiversity, provides water resources, and reduces vulnerability to natural disasters (Gweshengwe, 2025).

The literature also shows that NbS help address societal challenges by tackling pressing issues such as climate change through mitigation and adaptation (Mirsafa et al., 2025). Prodanovic et al. (2024) report that NbS reduces biodiversity loss and improves food and water security. Cheng and Li (2024) reveal that NbS helps reduce disasters such as floods and landslides. It is shown that NbS can also safeguard human health and well-being and ensure urban sustainability (Klaus et al., 2025). Furthermore, it is posited that NbS leverage the services often naturally provided by healthy ecosystems, such as water purification, climate regulation, pollination, and soil stabilisation (Cheng & Li, 2024; Gweshengwe, 2025).

The examples of NbS provided in the literature review include forest protection and restoration (Mashanye, Matamanda, & Bhanye, 2025). Reforestation, afforestation, and sustainable forest management are leveraged to absorb carbon, prevent erosion, regulate water cycles, and support biodiversity (Mirsafa et al., 2025). Wetland Restoration is another NbS example whereby wetlands are restored to mitigate floods, filter water, and provide habitat for wildlife (Mguni et al., 2025). Restoring mangrove forests, coral reefs, and dunes is another NbS example that serves to provide natural barriers against storm surges, erosion, and sea-level rise (Zyoud & Zyoud, 2025). Several studies also show sustainable agriculture as another example of NbS (Corgo et al., 2024; Klaus et al., 2025; Mirsafa et al., 2025). It is posited that practices such as agroforestry (integrating trees into farming systems) and climate-smart agriculture improve soil health, enhance biodiversity, and increase resilience to climate impacts (Cheng & Li, 2024; Gweshengwe, 2025). In addition, urban green infrastructure serves as another good example of NbS. Introducing green roofs, rain gardens, urban parks, and tree planting in cities can help to reduce urban heat island effects, manage stormwater, improve air quality, and enhance mental well-being (Cheng & Li, 2024; Zyoud & Zyoud, 2025). Ahmad and Hassan (2025) cite integrated water management as another NbS example, positing that using natural systems to manage water resources, such as protecting riverine ecosystems, can help to improve water quality and reduce flood risks.

Overall, NbS offers a powerful and integrated approach to creating a more sustainable and resilient future for SSA's food systems.

Method

Literature Search and Coding

This study adopts a systematic review methodology using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework. The framework guarantees a systematic and standardised procedure for identifying, screening, assessing eligibility, and extracting data from databases (Tedja, Al-Musadieq, Kusumawati, et al., 2024). Articles for review were obtained from Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus databases as the leading and most comprehensive databases containing peer-reviewed texts (Pranckutė, 2021). The keywords 'nature-based solutions' OR 'NbS' and 'Africa' or Sub-Saharan Africa were used to search for relevant articles from the two databases. Table 1 shows the retrieval limits used.

Table 1

Article Retrieval Limits from Selected Databases

Item	Description
Database	Scopus/Web of Science
Search field	Title, Abstract, Keywords
Keywords	Nature-based solutions, NbS, Africa,

Accessibility	Sub-Saharan Africa
Years	Open 01/01/2020 - 31/06/2025
Author name	Exclude undefined names
Subject area	All
Publication stage	Final
Document Type	All
Language	English

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Generic searches in the two databases yielded 120 articles (WoS = 77, Scopus = 43). The searches were further refined, and 41 and 26 articles were retained, respectively. The search for articles was done on 05 July 2025, and it was carried out from the title and abstract only to prevent irrelevant articles from being extracted. The articles were exported as CSV for manual screening and duplicate elimination. A total of 19 duplicates were removed, leaving 48 articles eligible for abstract screening. After the abstract screening, 42 articles were retained for further full-text screening.

Following the full-text screening, an additional six articles were eliminated for irrelevance, leaving 36 articles. This sample was considered adequate for a qualitative study. Table 2 shows more details on the exclusion and inclusion criteria adopted in the study. Figure 1 shows a summary of how the texts were identified for analysis.

Table 2

Article Identification Criteria

Inclusion criterion	Exclusion criterion
Peer-reviewed articles from Scopus and WoS.	Grey reviewed literature and articles found outside these two databases.
Articles published between 2020 and 2024	Articles published before 2020 and after 2024
Articles from both open-access and subscription-based publishers.	Articles from outside these open-access and subscription-based publishers.
Final papers	Articles in press
English	Articles written in other languages
Articles on agriculture or food systems in SSA	Articles outside SSA

Figure 1

Flowchart Summarising the Identification of Texts

Data Analysis

Content analysis - the study of the contents of a text- was used in this paper. The analysis was done manually. During analysis, texts were first coded into manageable classes. Segments of interest (quotations) were extracted from the relevant texts focusing on agriculture or food systems in Africa. Each of the segments was coded. Coding of the segments of interest was done manually. The quotations and codes were generated concurrently. The article employed both deductive and inductive coding for all the identified segments of interest in the remaining articles deemed relevant. Deductive coding was based on food systems components: production, storage, processing, distribution/transportation, retail, and consumption. In using content analysis, latent coding was adopted to generate an in-depth understanding of the issues under investigation. The author read through the texts to have an overall argument and position of the text. Thematic analysis a method in which themes are developed from available data was then used.

Limitations of the Study

Although the systematic review research approach attempts to eliminate bias in the review process, the effectiveness of systematic reviews depends on the availability of high-quality data sources. The author acknowledges that reliance on manual processes in content analysis can lead to inconsistencies in data interpretation. It is believed that the peer review by colleagues will help minimise such inconsistencies. A more rigorous and comprehensive evaluation of the data in the selected texts could be conducted to strengthen the evidence. However, such an additional assessment was beyond the scope of this article.

Findings: Leveraging Nature-based Solutions

The findings are presented under two sub-sections, namely, challenges of SSA food systems and the proposed NbS for SSA food system challenges.

Challenges of SSA Food Systems

The review identified several challenges for SSA food systems, including climate change impacts, conflict and instability, inadequate infrastructure, limited access to resources and markets, and the effects of global economic shocks (see Table 3). These factors contribute to widespread food and nutrition insecurity, hindering progress towards sustainable and equitable food systems. However, it was found that not all of these challenges can be resolved through NbS. For instance, challenges such as those related to conflicts and political instability, global shocks, and market-related challenges require interventions beyond NbS.

Table 3

Challenges of SSA Food Systems

Challenge	No of articles
Climate change	23
Conflict and instability	2
Inadequate infrastructure	3
Limited resources	3
Limited markets	2
Global shocks	3

The review also showed that identified challenges differed according to SSA sub-regions, with West Africa being the most affected, followed by Central Africa and East Africa. Southern Africa had the least number of articles focusing on it (see Table 4).

Table 4

Article Distribution per Sub-region

Sub-region	No of articles
West Africa	13
Central Africa	9
East Africa	8
Southern Africa	6

Proposed Categories of NbS

The analysis yielded three key categories of solutions into which the reviewed articles could be grouped in relation to NbS (see Table 5). Articles were categorised according to the aspect which they tended to emphasise most. Almost half of the articles (47%) linked NbS to climate change resilience, particularly regarding farming activities;

17% of the articles emphasised the capacity of NbS to ensure biodiversity welfare, and 36% emphasised the potential of NbS to address land degradation challenges.

Table 5

Categories of Solutions

Category	No of articles	Percentage
Climate change resilience	17	47
Biodiversity welfare	6	17
Address land degradation	13	36
Total	36	100

The main factors emanating from climate change, biodiversity disruption, and land degradation, which affect food systems, are summarised in Table 6. Changes in rainfall emerged as the biggest issue in 25% of the reviewed articles. This is because SSA's agricultural sector is dominated by smallholder farmers who practice rainfed farming (Ndhlovu, 2025a). 16% of the articles implicated drought, 11% blamed rising temperatures, and another 11% reported floods as the leading causes of the SSA food system's poor performance. The other factors that emerged included pests and diseases (3%), soil erosion (8.3%), nutrient loss (3%), salinisation (5.4%), water retention (3%), increased weeds (8.3%), low pollination (3%), and high production costs (3%).

Table 6

Sub-categories of SSA Food System Challenges

Category	No of articles	Percentage
Changes in rainfall	9	25
Changes in temperature	4	11
Drought	6	16
Flooding	4	11
Pests and diseases	1	3
Soil erosion	3	8.3
Nutrient loss	1	3
Salinisation	2	5.4
Reduced water retention	1	3
Increased weeds	3	8.3
Low pollination	1	3
High production costs	1	3
Total	36	100

The review showed that the identified challenges affect farming activities and food distribution, particularly when transport systems are disrupted by floods and storms (see Nébié, Ba, & Giannini, 2021; Onyeaka et al., 2024). Climate change and associated natural hazards, for instance, affect food production by eroding farms, destroying crops, and destroying critical infrastructure such as roads, bridges, and food storage facilities. It is argued that adopting NbS would enhance food system resilience by improving water retention on farms, reducing erosion, sequestering carbon, and diversifying agricultural production, making SSA food systems less vulnerable to shocks (Bedasa & Deksis, 2024; Salhi, El Hasnaoui, Pérez-Cutillas et al., 2023). The review also showed that since the majority of SSA farmers are smallholders who rely heavily on natural resources, it is vital that NbS tailored to local contexts be adopted to empower these farmers by reducing their reliance on expensive external inputs, improving yields, and diversifying livelihoods (Nyika & Dinka, 2022).

Biodiversity protection was another solution proposed for developing SSA food systems. This was proposed by 17% of the reviewed articles (see Table 5). SSA is home to incredible biodiversity, which is crucial for ecosystem services supporting agriculture by providing indispensable benefits that improve farm resilience, productivity, and sustainability (Birkhofer et al., 2024). The review showed that various ecosystems, including soil organisms, pollinators, and natural pest predators, contribute to healthy soils, effective pollination, and natural pest control, reducing the need for artificial inputs, like fertilisers and pesticides (Nyika & Dinka, 2022). The review also showed that maintaining crop and livestock diversity strengthens resilience against environmental stressors such as climate change and disease (Olago et al., 2024). It is revealed that NbS can protect and restore these natural assets, which in turn bolsters pollination, pest control, and soil health (Abdullahi et al., 2024).

The review identified land degradation as another challenge for SSA food systems. Land degradation is the reduction or loss of land's biological or economic productivity (Kgaphola et al., 2023). The reviewed articles showed that in SSA, land degradation is caused by various factors, including unsustainable land management practices, extreme weather events, and pollution (Abdullahi et al., 2024; Akpensuen & Rivero, 2025; de Jong et al., 2024). This degradation negatively impacts food production, livelihoods, and the overall health of ecosystems. Desertification and land degradation are reported as severe issues in many parts of Africa (Tefera et al., 2024). The review reported that NbS, such as agroforestry and conservation agriculture, are direct interventions to restore soil fertility, prevent erosion, and bring degraded land back into productivity.

Discussion: Integrating NbS in Food Systems

Although the reviewed articles do not provide a comprehensive overview of NbS solutions in SSA food systems, possibly due to the lack of empirical evidence to back up conclusions, the general sentiment is that these solutions can make a significant difference once adopted. NbS hold much potential to facilitate agroecology and regenerative agriculture in SSA. This can be achieved by mobilising SSA farmers to practice cover cropping, no-till farming, crop diversification and rotation, integrated pest management, and organic matter management. Many traditional SSA farming practices already integrate agroecological principles, offering a strong foundation for scaling up (Ndhlovu, 2025a). These practices can improve soil health, water retention, and biodiversity, reduce dependence on chemical fertilisers and pesticides, increase yields, boost climate resilience, and promote nutrient cycling.

NbS can also promote agroforestry in SSA agriculture. Farmers can be supported in integrating trees and shrubs into agricultural landscapes (e.g., planting trees on farms, silvopastoralism, and forest gardens). This will stabilise soils, lessen erosion, boost water quality, sequester carbon, provide shade for crops and livestock, offer additional income streams (fruits, fodder, timber, fuelwood), and boost biodiversity (Zerihun, 2021). On the African continent, projects such as the Great Green Wall initiative in the Sahel region are huge agroforestry efforts to fight desertification and improve livelihoods. In Ethiopia, Farm Africa's work has also successfully integrated agroforestry to improve drought resilience and food security.

Land and water management is a significant issue in SSA (Kgaphola et al., 2023; Tefera et al., 2024). NbS has the potential to

promote sustainable land and water management. This can be achieved by constructing terraces, contour farming, rainwater harvesting, conservation agriculture, restoration of degraded water catchments, and wetland restoration. This will improve water infiltration, reduce runoff and erosion, recharge groundwater, provide clean water for irrigation and consumption, and mitigate flood risks. Many communities already implement traditional and modern water harvesting techniques. Wetland restoration, as observed in Ethiopia, can secure government support by demonstrating benefits for both flood mitigation and livelihoods.

NbS can also facilitate coastal and aquatic ecosystem restoration. This can be achieved through restoring mangrove forests, coral reefs, and other coastal wetlands. This has the potential to protect coastal communities from storm surges and erosion, support fish populations that are crucial for food security, sequester carbon and enhance biodiversity. In East Africa, Kenyan communities are actively replanting mangroves to shield against storms and absorb greenhouse gases while also establishing seaweed farms for economic diversification (Prosperi et al., 2021).

NbS are often aligned with indigenous knowledge systems and traditional farming practices. Therefore, they can be leveraged to support what communities are already practising to sustain their livelihoods. NbS can incorporate centuries-old local knowledge on crop varieties, soil management, and water conservation that are inherently nature-based and adapted to local conditions. These solutions are highly localised and context-specific, can maintain the genetic diversity of crops, build on existing community expertise, and hence foster food sovereignty. Many SSA farming systems intrinsically integrate traditional knowledge, which should be recognised, supported, and scaled where appropriate (Liang et al., 2025; Ndhlovu & Dube, 2024).

There are, however, several challenges for SSA food system actors in transitioning to NbS. These challenges include limited finances and a lack of technical knowledge and training. Farmers and extension workers will need more training and capacity building on NbS implementation. Another challenge is weak policy and governance frameworks that often characterise SSA countries. Across all sub-regions, insufficient policies, incentives, and land tenure security can hinder adoption. SSA food system actors also face challenges of limited market access for products from NbS farming. This can disincentivise adoption. In addition, rapid population increase is also putting pressure on land resources, leading to unsustainable practices if not managed with NbS (Ndhlovu, 2025c). Furthermore, in fragile regions, large-scale projects can be challenging.

Notwithstanding these challenges, numerous opportunities exist to boost SSA food systems through NbS. These include the increasing global and regional recognition of NbS, attracting more funding and political will. NbS can also create 'green jobs and entrepreneurial opportunities for Africa's large youth population. In addition, combining NbS with appropriate technologies (e.g., climate information services, mobile extension) can amplify impact. Many successful NbS projects already exist across SSA, providing valuable lessons and models for replication. Furthermore, growing interest from the private sector in sustainable sourcing and climate-smart investments can unlock new financing.

Recommendations

To effectively leverage NbS for efficient, resilient, and sustainable

food systems in SSA, a multi-pronged approach is needed. This includes strengthening policy and governance. SSA countries need to develop national and regional policies that incentivise and support NbS adoption, clarify land tenure, and integrate NbS into agricultural and food system development strategies. The Green Growth and Climate Resilience Strategy, which allocates a budget to NbS in Rwanda, is a good example.

There is also a need for increased investment and financing. SSA countries need to mobilise public and private investment, including climate finance, to de-risk NbS projects and provide farmers with financial incentives (e.g., grants, subsidies, microfinance). Further, governments must invest in training, extension services, and farmer-to-farmer learning networks to improve technical skills and the responsiveness of NbS.

It is also vital that SSA governments provide funding for research and Development (R&D). Governments must support research to identify locally appropriate NbS, quantify their benefits, and adapt them to specific agroecological zones. In addition, there is a need for community engagement and empowerment. This will ensure that NbS initiatives are community-driven, respectful of indigenous knowledge, and empower local populations in decision-making and implementation. Furthermore, SSA governments need to adopt integrated landscape approaches, considering the interrelation of diverse ecosystems (farmlands, forests, wetlands) to maximise benefits. Moreover, governments need to implement monitoring and evaluation systems. SSA governments need to establish strong systems to monitor the impact of NbS on food security, livelihoods, and ecosystems to demonstrate their effectiveness and attract further investment.

By tactically investing in and scaling up NbS, SSA can transform its food systems, ensuring food security for its growing population while building resilience against climate shocks and conserving its invaluable natural heritage

Conclusion

This article explored the potential of NbS in transforming SSA's food systems. The article first identified the challenges of SSA's food systems and then explored how NbS can contribute to the realisation of efficient, resilient, and sustainable food systems in SSA. It found that although empirical studies on NbS and focusing on food systems are still limited in SSA, the general sentiment is that NbS yields much potential to provide solutions to SSA agricultural and food system challenges, such as climate change, biodiversity loss, land degradation, and increasing pests and diseases. It showed that NbS in SSA agriculture and food systems are vital for building sustainable and resilient food systems while mitigating climate change and enhancing biodiversity. They offer a pathway to transform current food systems into nature-positive ones by shielding natural resources and biodiversity. NbS utilises ecosystem functions to address challenges like soil erosion, water scarcity, and biodiversity loss, ultimately improving agricultural productivity and livelihoods.

There are, however, several challenges to the adoption of NbS in SSA food systems. These include limited finances and a lack of technical knowledge and training, weak policy and governance frameworks, insufficient policies, incentives, and land tenure security that hinder adoption, and limited market access for products from NbS farming. However, despite these challenges, the article showed that numerous opportunities exist to boost SSA food systems through NbS. These include the increasing global and regional

recognition of NbS, attracting more funding and political will. There is also growing interest from the private sector in sustainable sourcing, and climate-smart investments can unlock new financing. Future research should explore how funds can be mobilised to fund NbS adoption by SSA's farmers, most of whom are smallholder and peasant farmers.

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Received February 14, 2026

Revision received March 3, 2026

Accepted March 4, 2026